

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	Gabri Project
GPR	2011	B		Min: 61.539 Max: 62.151	1405 ☒ Natural ☐ Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No
 In elevation drawing? Yes No
 Photos: Yes No #: 1822-3
 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: Yellowish fill, south of road 1400.
 Covered by SU: 0
 Fills SU:
 Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX														
☒ Pottery ☐ Nails ☒ Tiles ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass	☒ Tufo (specify) <i>E (small-large)</i> ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☒ Basalt <i>E (small-large)</i> ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	clay 10% silt 80% sand 10% ☒ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>☐ Hard</td> <td>☐ Black ☐ Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td>☒ Compact</td> <td>☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td>☐ Friable</td> <td>☐ Light Gray ☐ White</td> </tr> <tr> <td>☐ Loose</td> <td>☒ Yellow ☐ Red</td> </tr> <tr> <td>☐ Soft</td> <td>☐ Light Yellow</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>☐ Other (specify)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Compaction	Color	☐ Hard	☐ Black ☐ Brown	☒ Compact	☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown	☐ Friable	☐ Light Gray ☐ White	☐ Loose	☒ Yellow ☐ Red	☐ Soft	☐ Light Yellow		☐ Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by: <i>su 1406</i>	Abuts: <i>1400, 1394, 1414, 1391</i>
Is covered by: <i>su 0</i>	Covers: <i>1425</i>
Is cut by: <i>su 1407 = 1175</i>	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
dry upper surface revealed, but not excavated

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: *S-W quarter, near corner.*
 Shape: *large N-S rectangle*
SU is still in situ

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):
Slopes slightly south

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): *no clusters. Large tufo inclusions*

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): *✓*

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify) *n.a.*

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SU 1405 Represents a probable ancient layer, but its position just below backfill layers from the old Italian excavations make it very likely that significant contamination occurred. 1405 probably represents a natural accumulation which post-dates the destruction of road 1400, but the exact relationship remains uncertain while 1405 awaits excavation.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by J. Hart

Revised by CHM

PDFd by ELR

Entered by FR

on 20/7/2011

on 21/7/2011

on 27/7/2011

on 28/7/2011